

An Update on Demographics and Diversity and Inclusion Efforts with the Belle II Collaboration

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Abstract

The Belle II collaboration comprises over 1000 international high energy physicists, who investigate the properties of b -quarks and other particles at the luminosity frontier. In order to achieve our aim of a successful physics program, it is essential that we emphasise contributions from a diverse community. Belle II has thus far focused on diversity in gender and sexuality, among other efforts within our collaboration. These efforts are led by our two Diversity Officers, elected to the newly created positions in 2018. Their role has been to promote an inclusive atmosphere, raising awareness of diversity and being a safe first point of call for issues of discrimination and harassment.

These proceedings accompany the talk of the same name, marking the fourth time that Belle II has presented in diversity and equity streams at high-energy physics conferences [6] [2] [3] [8]. It will describe details of the efforts described above, as well as examine the evolving demographics of our community, since membership began in 2011.

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1 Introduction

Over the next decade, the Belle II particle physics experiment will record billions of decays involving b -quarks, created in electron-positron collisions at the SuperKEKB accelerator in Tsukuba, Japan [1]. More than 1,000 Belle II collaborators engage in the physics program, affiliated with 188 institutes spread across 27 countries and regions. To ensure Belle II's success in high-precision measurements of particle physics parameters, it is imperative to encourage participation from a diverse range of collaborators.

Diversity describes the large range of differences between people, such as gender, race, sexual orientation, socio-economic status, ability etc. The diversity of wider society is not often seen in physics departments. For the case of gender, in the 2018 Global Survey of Mathematical, Natural and Computing Scientists, 37% of women reported physics as their primary field of study, despite 50% of respondents being women [7]. Inclusion describes the actions taken to support those who may not be seen as often in science, so as to give them an equitable opportunity to do good physics. Without inclusion actions, demographics will remain biased towards the majority, thus artificially limiting perspectives in progressing science. Belle II's efforts towards diversity and inclusion consist of monitoring gender demographics, summarised in Section 2, as well as developing equity initiatives, summarised in Section 3.

2 Demographics: Examining the Diversity of Belle II

The following section contains gender, institutional region, career stage, talk allocation and leadership role statistics of Belle II collaborators as of the most recent Japanese Financial Year (JFYear, with JFYear 2022 being April 1st 2022 - March 31st 2023). The Belle II Membership Management System (B2MMS) began in 2017 where collaborators self-report their gender, regional and career stage information when they sign on to the experiment. Prior to this, membership was managed by the Belle II Secretariat. As of 2022, collaborators can choose to specify their gender as 'male', 'female', 'other' or to leave this option blank, allowing for recognition of gender non-conforming collaborators. There are no requirements that this matches identity documentation such as passports. Records of unspecified gender between 2011 and 2017 are largely due to lack of information in the previous membership system, rather than declaration by members. As the current use of the categories of 'other' or blank gender are small, these are categorised with previous gender unspecified records in the following bar plots. It is important to note that gender non-conforming collaborators are also gender minorities in physics and thus gender inclusion efforts should extend beyond just women.

Figure 1 and Table 1 demonstrate the number of Belle II collaborators registered in 2022, by gender and geographical region. In contrast to other large high-energy physics collaborations, more than a third of Belle II members are associated with institutes in Asia. The percentage of women varies from 14.4% in North America to 21.6% in Asia countries, both well under the 37% found in the Global Survey mentioned in Section 1.

Figure 2 demonstrates the increase in number of Belle II collaborators since membership began in 2011, separated by gender. This large increase in total collaborators in 2018 coincides with the first collisions recorded by Belle II. The fraction of women within the collaboration has increased from 12.2% of 467 members in 2011, to 19.7%

Figure 1: Gender of Belle II collaborators according to region. Grouping of countries into regions follows that of a similar presentation by the ATLAS Collaboration and thus preserves anonymity of institutes [4]

Figure 2: Gender of Belle II collaborators, per Japanese Fiscal Year. This extends from 1st April of the given year, until March 31st of the following year. Membership records from 2011-2016 were managed by KEK, as opposed to the B2MMS.

Table 1: 2022 Belle II collaborator gender and region statistics. \uparrow and \downarrow indicate changes of 1% since Belle II's previous presentation[2]

Region	#People (N=1118)	%People (in Collaboration)	#Women (N=234)	%Women (in Region)
Japan	173	14.6	27	15.6 \downarrow
Asia (excluding Japan)	258	21.7 \uparrow	64	24.8 \uparrow
Eastern Europe	87	7.32 \downarrow	13	14.9 \downarrow
Mediterranean	194	16.3 \uparrow	42	21.6 \uparrow
North America	180	15.2	26	14.4 \uparrow
Northern Europe	269	22.6 \downarrow	57	21.2 \uparrow
Southern Hemisphere	27	2.27	5	18.5

of 1188 members in 2022. While this is an appreciable difference, naively extrapolating this trend suggests it would take over 50 years to reflect the proportion of women in the general population, longer than the planned lifetime of Belle II.

Figure 3 and Table 2 reports the 2022 proportions of Belle II collaborators differing career stages, by gender. Of note is that the percentage of women in junior positions is above 25%. This trend of decreasing percentages of women at each higher stage of academia may be evidence of the 'leaky pipeline effect' seen in wider physics communities. However, this may also be the case of a 'propagating wave', where increases in the number of women in junior stages may result in increases of women in permanent positions in the future. Such evidence is seen in Figure ?? shows the influx of new junior members after data taking commenced and Figure 5 similarly shows growth in proportion of women at these stages. The latter demonstrates larger increases in more junior positions, with a much steadier rate in permanent faculty. Large fluctuations, such as that of the proportion of woman

Figure 3: 2022 Gender of Belle II collaborators, according to career stage.

Table 2: 2022 Number of Belle II women by career stage

Stage	#People (in Collab)	% People	# Women (at Stage)	% Women
All	1188	100	234	19.8
UG.	92	7.74	26	28.3
PG.	398	33.5	106	26.6
Term.	141	11.9	26	18.4
Perm.	330	27.8	46	13.9
Tech.	227	19.1	30	13.2

undergraduates, are a result of lower statistics in these categories. Monitoring the rate of increase between career stages over time may allow distinguishing between the ‘pipeline’ and ‘wave’ cases.

Figure 5 demonstrates the percentage of women delivering talks and in leadership roles for Belle II. This next plot demonstrates the yearly involvement of women in our collaboration. This compares the fraction of women overall, the fraction of women chosen for external conference talks, the fraction offering internal plenary talks at our Belle II General Meetings (B2GM) and the fraction appointed to any leadership role, as well as in a senior role. The participation of women grows towards that of the overall collaboration, with choppiness in the trends due to the small number of women at each level. Of note is that of the 36 senior leadership roles in 2022, only 2 members are women.

3 Inclusion: Efforts to Improve our Diversity

In October 2017, the Belle II Code of conduct was amended to include a statement on diversity and inclusion, acknowledging that an array of experiences enriches, not diminishes, one’s learning [5]. All Belle II members are required to abide by the code.

Belle II has also had diversity officers since 2018. Their roles are to promote an inclusive collaboration, to provide a safe point of contact to report issues of discrimination, bullying, or harassment, to ensure those from marginalised groups are appropriately considered for positions of responsibility and to publicize the collaboration’s efforts to promote equity. Since the last talk delivered by Belle II in the diversity and inclusion stream, Steve Robertson and Emi Kou have been welcomed into the roles. They chair the diversity parallel sessions held at B2GMs, occurring three times a year at KEK, the facility which hosts the Belle II detector. These sessions act as forums for collaborators to voice concerns, becoming quite animated group discussions. A number of new concerns have been identified in this way, especially with the move back to in-person meetings after COVID. This includes difficulties in interpreting Japanese food labelling for those who visiting the experiment. This can lead to medical emergencies in the case of allergens, but also discourage collaborators with religious or other dietary requirements from joining meetings in

Figure 4: *Percentage of Belle II women at career stage, by year*

Figure 5: *Proportion of women delivering talks and in leadership roles at Belle II, since 2011.*

Japan. Moreover, expectations of face-to-face meetings excludes those in regions who may have difficulties with obtaining Visas or with small travel budgets. The officers have also received feedback on collaborators who struggle with attending online working group meetings due to incompatible timezones, with some not able to take leadership positions or not attending at all to avoid working in night hours. Solutions to these are not one-size-fits-all, but are being monitored with the goal of developing ‘best-practice’ documents that can advise working groups in the future. To assess the experiences of the wider Belle II collaboration, not only those who are able to attend the parallel sessions, a new survey is being deployed. This is the second such survey we have done, with the first being done in 2018. Previous Belle II surveys have led to more equitable arrangements - gender neutral and accessible bathrooms closer to the experimental control room were installed, as there were only urinals available before. Some difficulties from the last survey were obtaining student responses, collaborator concerns about being identified based on answers, as well as the length of the survey itself. The updated version was run in March 2023, allowing collaborators to skip questions that may not be relevant to them, or they may not want to answer. Sections were added about the impact that COVID and the war in Ukraine may have had on collaborators. Due to the concerns about how the data would be stored, the survey was moved from Google Forms to an external platform LimeSurvey. To ensure confidentiality, individual responses were only accessible by those analysing the data, the diversity officers. This analysis of the results is ongoing, though new issues have already been identified, such as differences in country of origin vs country of work, as well as differences in expectations regarding non-binary genders. An interesting take-away was the larger ratio of respondents identifying as non-binary than declared in the B2MMS. This is potentially as collaborators felt it was safer to provide this anonymously in the survey, rather than having their gender explicitly matched to their name in the B2MMS. New developments in the B2MMS allow for collaborators to declare their personal pronouns. This information can be looked up by collaborators, allowing for more sensitive communications amongst members. The diversity officers have also encouraged members to include their pronouns on nametags and presentations during

general meetings. This is done with the intention raising awareness amongst collaborators, given that the survey has demonstrated there are differing levels of public understanding of non-binary genders throughout the world. It has been emphasised by the officers that using and respecting personal pronouns are not a matter of politics, grammar, or a given country's LGBTQ+ laws, but about human dignity and common courtesy.

4 Conclusion

The Belle II Diversity Officers will continue to monitor collaboration demographics and raise awareness of diversity and inclusion. The goal of this is not only to create a better collaboration for members, but to make high energy physics a more inclusive space as a whole. and better the field of Physics as a whole. It is through support for underrepresented groups that we obtain more diverse approaches to analysis and thus better Physics.

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